

Synthesis, Characterisation and Surfactant Behaviours of Acylaminoethyl Esters of Fatty Acids

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Acylaminoethyl esters of myristic, stearic, 12-hydroxystearic, oleic, ricinoleic and erucic acids have been synthesised at 60° using immobilised lipase as catalyst through the esterification of monoethanolamine with the respective fatty acid. Various surfactant properties of the synthesised esters have been evaluated and compared.

Non-ionic surfactants are the fastest growing group of emulsifying agents. In many ways the hydrophobic and hydrophilic moieties of the molecule may be modified to make tailor-made emulsifier for a particular application. Many ether, ester and amide-linked emulsifiers are commercially available.

The use of oleochemicals as renewable raw materials for the preparation of surfactants is becoming increasingly important and remarkable advances have been made in this direction¹. Enzymes as biocatalysts are being used to synthesise compounds. The biochemical reactions are selective, less energy-consuming and environmentally safe. Hence the orientation is directed towards the gradual replacement of the conventional chemical reaction by enzymatic reaction.

Lipase is used as a biocatalyst to synthesise a great variety of compounds. Lipase from *Mucor miehei* (Syn. *Rhizomucor miehei*) has been used to synthesise amides from amines and acids² in organic solvent medium. *R. miehei* lipase immobilised on anion exchange resin (Lipozyme IM-20) has been used as catalyst for the preparation of fatty amides from fatty acid methyl esters and *N*-alkylamine in hexane medium³. Fatty esters have also been synthesised by condensation of isopropylidene glycerol and oleic acid using the same Lipozyme catalyst⁴. Literature survey reveals that fatty acid monoethanolamide, and excellent surfactant, is obtained by the conventional chemical reaction in a two-step process⁵. The fatty acid first re-

acts with monoethanolamine (in 2 : 1 molar ratio) to give fatty acid acylaminoethyl ester, which in turn reacts with another mole of monoethanolamine to yield the fatty acid amide. The present work is directed towards the synthesis of such surfactants through enzymatic reaction using immobilised lipase from *R. miehei*.

We present herein the synthesis of hitherto unreported acylaminoethyl esters of myristic, steric, 12-hydroxysteric, oleic, ricinoleic and erucic acids at ~60° using immobilised lipase of *R. miehei* (Lipozyme IM-20) as catalyst,

Fatty acid . Monoethanolamine

These compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis, ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. Their surfactant properties, viz. surface tension, foam stability, contact angle, wetting and emulsifying power have been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The ir and ¹H nmr spectral data of the acylamino

TABLE 1-SPECTRAL DATA OF THE FATTY ACID ACYLAMINOETHYL ESTERS*

Compd./ (Mol. form., mol. wt.)	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	¹ H nmr ppm
Myristic acid acylaminoethyl ester (C ₃₀ H ₅₉ NO ₃ , 481)	1 720 (C=O of ester), 1 640 (CONH), 3 300 (NH)	0.85-0.90 (6H, t, CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (44H, s, CH ₂), 2.2-2.3 (4H, q, CH ₂ CO), 3.4 5-3.65 (2H, m, CH ₂ -N-CO-), 4.15-4.25 (2H, t, CH ₂ -O-CO-), 5.8(1H, b, N-H)
Stearic acid acylaminoethyl ester (C ₃₈ H ₇₅ NO ₃ , 593)	1 720 (C=O of ester), 1 640 (CONH), 3 300 (NH)	0.85-0.90 (6H, t, CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (60H, s, CH ₂), 2.2-2.3 (4H, q, CH ₂ CO), 3.45-3.65 (2H, m, CH ₂ -N-O-CO-), 5.8(1H, b, N-H)
12-Hydroxystearic acid acylaminoethyl ester (C ₃₈ H ₇₅ NO ₅ , 625)	1 720 (C=O of ester), 1 640 (CONH), 3 350-3 250 (NH and OH overlapped)	0.85-0.90 (6H, t, CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (56H, s, CH ₂), 2.2-2.3 (4H, q, CH ₂ CO), 3.45-3.65 (2H, m, CH ₂ -N-CO-), 3.65 (2H, b, CH-OH), 4.15-4.25 (2H, t, CH ₂ -O-CO-), 5.8(1H, b, N-H)
Oleic acid acylaminoethyl ester (C ₃₈ H ₇₁ NO ₃ , 589)	1 720 (C=O of ester), 1 640 (CONH), 3 300 (NH)	0.85-0.90 (6H, t, CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (44H, s, CH ₂), 2.0-2.1 (8H, d, CH ₂ -C=), 2.2-2.3 (4H, q, CH ₂ CO), 3.45-3.65 (2H, m, CH ₂ -N-CO-), 4.15-4.25 (2H, t, CH ₂ -O-CO-), 5.3-5.4 (4H, q, CH=CH), 5.8 (1H, b, N-H)
Ricinoleic acid acylaminoethyl ester (C ₃₈ H ₇₁ NO ₃ , 589)	1 720 (C=O of ester), 1 640 (CONH), 3 350-2 250 (NH and OH overlapped)	0.85-0.90 (6H, t, CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (40H, s, CH ₂), 2.0-2.1 (8H, d, CH ₂ -C=), 2.2-2.3 (4H, q, CH ₂ CO), 3.45-3.65 (2H, m, CH ₂ -N-CO-), 3.65 (2H, b, CH-OH), 4.15-4.25 (2H, t, CH ₂ -O-CO-), 5.3-5.4 (4H, q, CH=CH), 5.8 (1H, b, N-H)
Erucic acid acylaminoethyl ester (C ₄₆ H ₈₇ NO ₃ , 701)	1 720 (C=O of ester), 1 640 (CONH), 3 300 (NH)	0.85-0.90 (6H, t, CH ₃), 1.2-1.3 (60H, s, CH ₂), 2.0-2.1 (8H, d, CH ₂ -C=), 2.2-2.3 (4H, q, CH ₂ CO), 3.5-3.65 (2H, m, CH ₂ -N-CO-), 4.15-4.25 (2H, t, CH ₂ -O-CO-), 5.3-5.4 (4H, q, CH=CH), 5.8 (1H, b, N-H)

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

esters are given in Table 1. Surfactant properties (Table 2), emulsification property (Table 3) and CMC and HLB data (Table 4) are also presented. Plots of surface tension vs concentration are shown in Fig. 1.

In general, all the compounds exhibited good sur-

face active properties. This can be attributed to the greater affinity of $-NHCO-$ group towards water and their optimum HLB values. The surface tension values increased with the increasing fatty acid chain-length of the hydrophobic moiety. However, the pres-

TABLE 2—SURFACTANT PROPERTIES OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF THE ACYLAMIOETHYL ESTERS

Compd.	Nature	Concn. (%, w/w)	Foam height (cm)		Foam stability (B/A)	Surface tension (dynes cm^{-1} at 25°)	Contact angle at 25° ^c	Wetting power (times)
			Initial ^a (A)	Final ^b (B)				
Myristic acid acylaminoethyl ester	Solid	0.10	13.0	12.2	0.938	33.5	39.8	32
		0.20	13.5	12.7	0.940	33.4	39.0	28
		0.50	13.8	13.0	0.942	33.4	38.4	25
		0.75	14.2	13.4	0.944	33.4	37.0	24
		1.00	14.4	13.9	0.965	33.4	35.4	20
Stearic acid acylaminoethyl ester	Solid	0.10	13.5	12.8	0.948	36.1	40.4	46
		0.20	13.6	12.9	0.948	36.1	40.2	44
		0.50	14.0	13.3	0.950	36.1	40.1	40
		0.75	14.2	13.5	0.950	36.0	40.0	36
		1.00	14.3	13.7	0.958	36.0	39.8	32
12-Hydroxystearic acid acylaminoethyl ester	Solid	0.10	13.2	12.4	0.939	31.5	38.2	30
		0.20	13.4	12.6	0.940	31.5	38.0	28
		0.50	13.7	13.0	0.949	31.4	37.0	24
		0.75	14.3	13.8	0.965	31.4	35.2	20
		1.00	14.5	14.2	0.979	31.4	33.4	16
Oleic acid acylaminoethyl ester	Liquid	0.10	8.4	7.7	0.917	34.1	39.4	46
		0.20	8.8	8.2	0.932	34.1	38.2	42
		0.50	9.0	8.5	0.944	34.1	36.6	37
		0.75	9.4	9.0	0.957	34.0	36.4	32
		1.00	9.6	9.2	0.958	34.0	36.0	30
Ricinoleic acid acylaminoethyl ester	Liquid	0.10	8.1	7.5	0.926	36.1	39.0	32
		0.20	8.7	8.2	0.942	36.1	38.2	28
		0.50	9.2	8.7	0.945	36.1	36.1	24
		0.75	9.5	9.1	0.958	36.0	35.0	22
		1.00	9.9	9.5	0.960	36.0	34.2	18
Erucic acid acylaminoethyl ester	Liquid	0.10	6.6	6.0	0.909	43.2	42.2	48
		0.20	6.9	6.3	0.913	42.0	39.0	46
		0.50	7.1	6.6	0.929	41.9	38.6	45
		0.75	7.4	7.0	0.945	41.8	38.2	42
		1.00	7.8	7.4	0.949	41.8	38.0	40

^aImmediately after the first solution was dropped.

^bAfter 5 min.

^cContact angle of distilled water (at 25°) = 46°.

^dWetting power time in distilled water = 75 s.

TABLE 3-EMULSIFICATION PROPERTY^a OF THE ACYLAMINOETHYL ESTERS

Time for separation of emulsion (s)					
Myristic acid ester	Stearic acid ester	12-Hydroxy-stearic acid ester	Oleic acid ester	Ricinoleic acid ester	Erucic acid ester
980	920	1960	1640	1885	860

^aEmulsification property at 30° with respect to groundnut oil using 1% aqueous solution (time for separation of 10 ml of aqueous phase, s)

Fig. 1. Plots of surface tension vs concentration of the acylaminoethyl esters of (Δ) myristic, (◇) 12-hydroxystearic, (×) ricinoleic, (■) oleic, (□) stearic and (●) erucic acids

ence of double bond and hydroxyl group in the fatty acid back-bone decreased the surface tension as exhibited by the oleic, hydroxystearic and ricinoleic acid esters. The erucic acid ester did not follow the general trend probably due to its very long chain-length.

All the acylaminoethyl esters exhibited reasonably good foaming ability. However, the esters of saturated fatty acids like myristic, stearic and 12-hydroxystearic acids showed superior foaming power in comparison to the esters of unsaturated fatty acids. The erucic acid ester was found to be least foaming among the synthesised compounds. The foam stability of the acylaminoethyl ester of 12-hydroxystearic acid was found to be superior amongst the compounds.

Though all the compounds formed good emulsion with vegetable oils, the compounds having double

bond or hydroxyl group in the hydrophobic moiety demonstrated better emulsifying power. Unfolding of the bulkier molecules like the hydroxyacid-based esters, at the oil-water interface, is more restricted than with those having smaller molecules like myristic, stearic or oleic acid. This restriction would minimise the coalescence of the droplets in the aqueous phase and in effect enhance emulsification and stability. Among the esters containing hydroxy acids, ricinoleic acid ester was found to have inferior emulsification property to that of 12-hydroxystearic acid ester. This may be due to the presence of double bond in the fatty acid back-bone of ricinoleic acid.

In case of wetting power, as indicated by contact angle and Drave tests, the acylaminoethyl esters of C₁₆-saturated, C₁₈-enoic and hydroxyenoic acid exhibited superior performance.

Experimental

Myristic, stearic, oleic, erucic (all L. R. grade), 12-hydroxystearic and ricinoleic acids (commercial grade) were used after purification. Monoethanolamine, hexane, methanol, chloroform, petroleum ether and diethyl ether (A. R.; S. D. Fine Chemicals) were used as such. Lipozyme IM-20, a *R. miehei* lipase immobilised on an anion exchange resin (Novo Nordisk, Denmark) was used as catalyst.

Acylaminoethyl ester: To the fatty acid (0.1 mol) dissolved in CHCl₃ (100 ml), Lipozyme IM-20 (10%, w/w, based on the reactants) was added with stirring followed by slow addition of monoethanolamine (0.05 mol). The reaction mixture was then refluxed at 60° for ~16 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by estimating the unreacted fatty acid in the aliquots drawn at different time intervals and also estimating the formation of water (Dean and Stark apparatus). The catalyst was removed by filtration after completion of the reaction. Chloroform was then evaporated off and the product extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and filtered. The solvent was distilled off and the traces removed under vacuum. The product was purified further by column chromatography using chloroform-hexane-methanol (5 : 6 : 1, by vol) as the eluent followed by elution with methanol. Purity of the product was ascertained by tlc on silica gel using chloroform-hexane-methanol (5 : 6 : 1, by vol) as solvent system.

A similar reaction was carried out in the absence of lipase but no such products were formed under the reaction conditions.

A Hewlett-Packard 5698 instrument was used for elemental analysis. Ir spectra (neat/nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Jeol FX 100 spectrometer (100 MHz).

Various surfactant properties of the aqueous solutions of the esters were evaluated. A Du'Nouy

tensiometer (S. D. Hardson & Co.) was used for measuring surface tension, a Ross-Miles apparatus (Bhanu Scientific and Instruments, India) for measuring foam height⁶ and a D-1060 (Kayeness, U.S.A.) instrument for measuring contact angle⁷. Wetting power⁸ and emulsifying property⁹ were determined following standard methods.

Equilibrium surface tension and critical micelle concentration (CMC) were determined from the surface tension-concentration data. The HLB values were calculated using the standard formulas¹⁰ :

TABLE 4—HLB VALUES OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF THE ACYLAMINOETHYL ESTERS BY DIFFERENT TECHNIQUES AT 25°

Compd.	Concn. of solution % (w/w)	Surfac tension dyne cm^{-1}	Equilibrium surface tension	CMC g dm^{-3}	HLB value	
					Method A	Method B
Myristic acid acylaminoethyl ester	0.005	42.9				
	0.010	40.0				
	0.025	37.3				
	0.050	35.1				
	0.075	33.5	33.5	7.5×10^{-2}	14.28	14.34
	0.10	33.5				
	0.15	33.5				
	0.20	33.4				
	0.50	33.4				
	1.00	33.4				
Stearic acid acylaminoethyl ester	0.005	41.0				
	0.010	39.8				
	0.025	38.4				
	0.050	37.2				
	0.075	36.4	36.1	9.5×10^{-2}	15.20	15.02
	0.10	36.1				
	0.15	36.1				
	0.20	36.1				
	0.50	36.0				
	1.00	36.0				
12-Hydroxystearic acid acylaminoethyl ester	0.005	40.5				
	0.010	37.5				
	0.025	34.6				
	0.050	32.0				
	0.075	31.5	31.5	6×10^{-2}	13.44	13.52
	0.10	31.5				
	0.15	31.5				
	0.20	31.4				
	0.50	31.4				
	1.00	31.4				

Table-4 (contd.)

Oleic acid	0.005	40.0				
acylaminoethyl ester	0.010	38.4				
	0.025	36.5				
	0.050	35.2				
	0.075	34.2	34.1	8.05×10^{-2}	14.51	14.56
	0.10	34.1				
	0.15	34.1				
	0.20	34.1				
	0.50	34.1				
	1.00	34.0				
Ricinoleic acid	0.005	42.0				
acylaminoethyl ester	0.010	40.0				
	0.025	37.2				
	0.050	35.2				
	0.075	34.0	33.7	8.1×10^{-2}	14.35	14.61
	0.10	33.7				
	0.15	33.7				
	0.20	33.7				
	0.50	33.7				
	1.00	33.6				
Erucic acid	0.005	49.5				
acylaminoethyl ester	0.010	47.9				
	0.025	46.1				
	0.050	45.1				
	0.075	43.8	42.0	17.5×10^{-2}	17.50	16.18
	0.10	43.2				
	0.15	42.4				
	0.20	42.0				
	0.50	41.9				
	1.00	41.8				

Method A :

$$HLB = 1.55 + 0.38 \gamma_{eq}$$

where γ_{eq} is the equilibrium surface tension of the surfactant.

Method B :

$$\frac{1}{HLB} = \frac{0.01076}{(\log CMC + 1.671)} + 0.05$$

where CMC represents the concentration of the surfactant at equilibrium surface tension.

References

1. R. TSUSHIMA, S. TAGATA, Y. YOKOTA and A. FUJII, *INFORM*, 1993, **4**, 680.
2. D. MONTET, M. PINA, J. GRAILLE, G. RENARD and J. GRIMAUD, *Fat. Sci. Technol.*, 1989, **91**, 14
3. R. G. BISTLINE, JR., A. BILYK and S. H. FEAIRHELLER, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 95
4. S. PECNIK and Z. KNEZ, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 261.
5. H. MAAG, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 259.
6. J. ROSS and S. D. MILES, *Oil Soap*, 1941, **18**, 99
7. GUASTELLA, 'Proceedings of the International Conference on Surface Activity', London, 1957, Vol., 3, p. 143.
8. Indian Standards IS : 5785 (Part V)-1981.
9. V. V. R. SUBRAHMANYAM and K. T. ACHAYA, *Chem. Eng. Data*, 1961, **6**, 38
10. H. SCHOTT, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1969, **58**, 1131.